

Observatoire ARGA

ARGA Atlas

The Use of Criminal Prosecution in Corporate Conflicts Across the Post-Soviet Region

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1. Definition of a Corporate Conflict

A corporate conflict, as a legal phenomenon, arises from either unlawful or lawful actions undertaken by other participants in corporate relations or by third parties. It constitutes a legal obstacle that adversely affects the corporate rights and/or legitimate interests of the parties involved by preventing the exercise of those rights or creating a threat to their future exercise. A corporate conflict represents a particular state of corporate legal relations, giving rise to protective legal relationships and requiring the reconciliation of the parties' interests. Such conflicts are intended to be resolved through mechanisms established by law and/or by agreements concluded between the founders or shareholders. All participants are presumed to seek resolution through these mechanisms. Where such efforts fail, the corporate conflict progresses to the next stage—a corporate dispute.

Accordingly, a corporate conflict may be defined as disagreements and disputes arising between the founders (shareholders) of a company, between founders (shareholders) and company management, or between investors (including prospective shareholders) and the company itself, which may result in one or more of the following consequences:

- violations of applicable legislation, the company's charter, or internal corporate regulations;
- infringement of the rights of one or more founders or shareholders;
- litigation against the company or its governing bodies concerning corporate decisions;
- premature termination of the powers of corporate management bodies; or
- significant changes in the composition of shareholders or founders.

2. Definition of Corporate Raiding

Throughout the post-Soviet region, criminal prosecution is frequently used in the context of corporate conflicts as a means of acquiring business assets through corporate raiding.

Legal scholarship generally defines corporate raiding as unlawful activity carried out against the will of a company's management with the objective of acquiring ownership, possession, use, or control of a company's assets, or obtaining control over the company itself through the acquisition of ownership rights in shares of a limited liability company or voting shares in a joint-stock company.

Corporate raiding follows recurring patterns that can be identified in thousands of cases across the post-Soviet region. Investigators, prosecutors, judges, tax officials, and enforcement officers each perform a functional role within a system that outwardly resembles the ordinary administration of justice but, in substance, serves the opposite purpose. The existence of this phenomenon has been acknowledged by various international institutions.

Neither the Criminal Code of the Russian Federation nor that of the Republic of Belarus contains a specific offence entitled "corporate raiding." Instead, prosecutors rely on a range of criminal offences that address individual elements of coercive or fraudulent business takeovers. By contrast, certain other post-Soviet jurisdictions have introduced a specific criminal offence expressly criminalizing corporate raiding.

3. Historical Background to the Use of Criminal Prosecution in Corporate Conflicts Across the Post-Soviet Region

According to the OECD report *Combatting High-Level Corruption in Eastern Europe* (12 September 2024), the use of law enforcement agencies to facilitate corporate raiding across the

post-Soviet region is closely linked to systemic corruption and institutional weakness. Weak adherence to the rule of law and ineffective law enforcement have fostered a culture of impunity in which corrupt public officials operate with little fear of accountability.

Following the dissolution of the Soviet Union, the countries of the Eastern Partnership experienced rapid privatization and extensive political and economic transformation. Weak regulatory frameworks and inadequate institutional oversight created significant opportunities for corruption, contributing to the emergence of crony capitalism and the unlawful enrichment of politically connected individuals. At the same time, efforts to combat high-level corruption have frequently encountered resistance from senior public officials and influential vested interests who benefit from maintaining the existing system. Such resistance has taken the form of deprioritizing anti-corruption efforts, undermining reform initiatives, and weakening the specialized institutions established to combat corruption.

The Russian Federation provides a particularly illustrative example. The privatization of state-owned property, which began in 1992, not only transferred public assets into private ownership but also strengthened the complex relationships that had developed between state institutions and organized criminal groups. The emerging business elite included former KGB officers, military defectors, government officials, and former prisoners.

As a consequence of the particular nature of the post-Soviet transition, a relatively small group of individuals acquired control over vast economic resources and became indispensable to the newly established political authorities, which depended upon them for financial resources and political support. In practice, a substantial proportion of the former assets of the Soviet Union came under the control of a limited number of businessmen—commonly referred to as oligarchs—whose economic influence translated into significant political power. Ministers, senior government officials, and officers of the Federal Security Service (FSB) have been described as “silent partners” of influential oligarchs, protecting their enterprises and promoting their interests at the state level (Eurasia Institutes, *Post-Soviet Organized Crime: Insights from Russia*, 2019).

Accordingly, historical developments across the post-Soviet region created conditions that enabled politically influential business elites to extend their influence beyond the economic sphere into political and state institutions. Systemic corruption, patronage networks, and weaknesses in judicial independence have become key factors contributing to the use of criminal prosecution as an instrument in corporate conflicts.

4. Reasons for the Use of Criminal Prosecution in Corporate Conflicts

From a legal perspective, corporate conflicts fall within the sphere of corporate law. However, as noted above, in many post-Soviet jurisdictions such conflicts are frequently accompanied by criminal proceedings and are resolved not before commercial (arbitrazh) courts but within the ordinary criminal justice system.

This tendency has been reinforced by the growing practice of initiating criminal proceedings in order to circumvent the established judicial mechanisms for resolving commercial disputes. Rather than seeking judicial protection through commercial litigation, one party proceeds directly to law enforcement authorities with a request to initiate criminal prosecution against the opposing party.

Reasons Why Many Corporate Conflicts Are Resolved Through Criminal Prosecution

Several factors explain why corporate conflicts in the post-Soviet region are frequently addressed through criminal proceedings rather than civil or commercial litigation:

- A more flexible approach to obtaining and admitting evidence than is available in civil proceedings. During criminal investigations, documentary evidence can be obtained through searches and seizures, while witness testimony can be collected through formal interrogations. As a result, obtaining admissible evidence is often considerably easier within the framework of criminal procedure than through ordinary civil litigation.
- The possibility of pursuing civil claims within criminal proceedings, provided that the claimant demonstrates that the damage resulted directly from the alleged criminal offence.

At the same time, judges hearing criminal cases arising from corporate conflicts often lack sufficient expertise in economics and corporate law. Fundamental concepts of corporate law—including limited liability, the separate legal personality of corporate entities, joint-stock companies, corporate losses, joint and several liability, the exercise of shareholders’ rights, declaration and payment of dividends, corporate control, the distinction between corporate interests and shareholders’ interests, fiduciary responsibilities, affiliated persons, and related-party transactions—are frequently interpreted through the lens of criminal law rather than corporate law.

In addition to procedural considerations, broader political and institutional factors also play an important role. Given the volume of criminal cases handled by ordinary courts, judges often have limited capacity to devote adequate attention to the complex legal and economic issues presented by corporate disputes.

Criminal proceedings should not be used as a substitute for civil or commercial litigation, just as the pre-trial detention of a businessperson should never serve as a mechanism of coercion or commercial pressure.

5. Typical Patterns of Criminal Prosecution in Corporate Conflicts

Although the legal mechanisms employed in corporate raiding vary, their underlying objective remains consistent: to create legal conditions so burdensome that the owner is compelled either to surrender the business asset voluntarily or is prevented from exercising effective control over it, thereby facilitating its acquisition by others.

The most common patterns include the following.

Scheme 1: “Fraud in the Incorporation of the Company”

One of the most common instruments of corporate raiding is the initiation of criminal proceedings for fraud allegedly committed during the establishment of the company or the execution of the founding agreements.

Typically, many years after the business has been established and has become commercially successful, a claimant—often a former business partner or a nominal shareholder—asserts that he or she was misled during the incorporation process, did not understand the terms of the founding agreement, or signed the relevant documents as a result of deception. On the basis of these allegations, criminal fraud proceedings are initiated against the actual owner of the business.

Scheme 2: “Tax Prosecution as a Lever”

Tax-related criminal proceedings represent one of the most effective instruments of pressure on businesses because of the characteristics of tax legislation throughout much of the post-Soviet region. The complexity of tax laws, inconsistent enforcement practices, and the broad discretion afforded to tax authorities make virtually any active business susceptible to tax-related allegations.

The scheme generally follows a predictable sequence. The tax authority initiates an unscheduled audit, frequently following an anonymous complaint or information received from law enforcement agencies. The audit identifies alleged tax violations, which may be genuine, exaggerated, or fabricated. The audit report is then forwarded to the investigative authorities, who initiate criminal proceedings for tax evasion.

Simultaneously, company bank accounts are frozen, assets become subject to precautionary seizure, and the company's ability to conduct ordinary commercial transactions is significantly restricted. Under these conditions, the business rapidly loses both liquidity and market value. At this stage, a prospective purchaser often emerges, offering to acquire the business at a substantially discounted price while claiming to "resolve the problem." In such cases, the true objective of the tax prosecution is not the recovery of unpaid taxes but the creation of conditions that compel the owner to dispose of the business under economic duress.

Indicators suggesting that tax prosecution is being used instrumentally rather than for legitimate law enforcement purposes include:

- the commencement of a tax audit immediately following a dispute with an influential individual or public authority;
- tax claims concerning reporting periods that had previously passed tax inspections without objection;
- the simultaneous initiation of multiple additional criminal investigations based on relatively minor allegations; and
- attempts by intermediaries to negotiate an informal settlement or the "closure" of the criminal case.

Scheme 3: "Criminal Proceedings as an Instrument of Corporate Takeover"

The most direct form of corporate raiding involves the use of criminal proceedings to alter corporate control over a company.

Under this model, the owner or chief executive officer is detained on allegations of fraud, embezzlement, or abuse of authority. While held in pre-trial detention or subject to travel restrictions, the individual is effectively prevented from managing the company. As part of the criminal proceedings, the court orders the seizure of the individual's shares or ownership interests.

Individuals acting on behalf of, or affiliated with, those seeking to acquire the business are then introduced into the company's governing bodies through corporate procedures that the legitimate owner is unable to challenge effectively while under criminal prosecution.

At the same time, corporate documentation is frequently manipulated or falsified. Minutes of shareholders' meetings may be created retrospectively, amendments may be made to the company's charter, and ownership rights relating to intellectual property or other key assets may be re-registered. By the time the criminal proceedings are discontinued or ultimately collapse before the courts, legal ownership and effective control of the business have often already been transferred to new owners.

6. Recognition by International Institutions of the Use of Criminal Prosecution in Corporate Conflicts and the High Level of Corruption

The European Court of Human Rights (ECtHR) has developed extensive case-law concerning post-Soviet States—particularly the Russian Federation, Ukraine, and Moldova—in which criminal proceedings resulted in the transfer of business assets to third parties.

Gusinskiy v. Russia

In *Gusinskiy v. Russia*, the Court found a violation of Article 18 of the European Convention on Human Rights, which prohibits the misuse of restrictions on Convention rights for purposes other than those prescribed by the Convention. The ECtHR concluded that “the criminal prosecution of the applicant was used to intimidate him” (paragraph 76).

Khodorkovskiy and Lebedev v. Russia (First Judgment, 25 July 2013)

In its first judgment, the ECtHR found violations of Article 6 of the Convention, which guarantees the right to a fair trial.

The Court held that the applicants had been denied the opportunity to communicate confidentially with their defence lawyers and that the collection and examination of evidence had been conducted unfairly.

The ECtHR further concluded that the refusal of the domestic courts to summon for examination the two experts who had prepared the prosecution’s economic expert report violated Article 6 §§1 and 3(d) of the Convention, which guarantees the right to examine or have examined witnesses against the accused. The Court emphasized that the expert report constituted a central element of the prosecution’s case, since its conclusions formed the basis for several of the charges brought against the applicants.

The defence had neither participated in the preparation of the expert report nor been afforded an opportunity to propose questions to the experts during earlier stages of the proceedings. Moreover, the defence had demonstrated before the trial court why the experts’ examination was necessary, and no legitimate reason existed for refusing their appearance.

The Court also criticized the domestic courts for rejecting, on purely formal grounds, evidence submitted by the defence, including audit reports prepared by Ernst & Young and PricewaterhouseCoopers. Those reports directly addressed the substance of the allegations and the conclusions reached by the prosecution’s experts.

According to the ECtHR, the defence was thereby placed at a significant procedural disadvantage. While the prosecution retained exclusive control over the appointment of experts, the formulation of questions, and the presentation of expert opinions, the defence was limited to submitting opinions prepared by specialists, who possess a different procedural status under Russian criminal procedure law and lack access to the complete case materials. The domestic courts refused to consider those opinions, preventing the defence from effectively challenging the prosecution’s expert evidence. The ECtHR concluded that this violated the principle of equality of arms.

Khodorkovskiy and Lebedev v. Russia (Second Judgment, 14 January 2020)

In its second judgment, delivered on 14 January 2020, the ECtHR again found a violation of Article 6(1) of the Convention concerning the applicants' right to a fair trial (paragraph 533 of the judgment).

In its successive evaluation reports, the Group of States against Corruption (GRECO) has consistently concluded that corruption constitutes a widespread systemic phenomenon within the Russian Federation, affecting public administration as a whole, including law enforcement agencies, the judiciary, and institutions responsible for preventing corruption. Although, prior to 2022, the Russian Federation implemented certain GRECO recommendations concerning the prevention of corruption within the executive branch, judiciary, and law enforcement authorities, GRECO continued to identify systemic deficiencies.

Against this background, the use of criminal prosecution in corporate conflicts has been facilitated by several structural factors, including systemic corruption among public officials, insufficient judicial expertise in corporate and commercial law, limited judicial independence from law enforcement authorities, and the absence of effective accountability mechanisms for judges responsible for unlawful convictions.

Furthermore, Russian procedural law grants prejudicial (preclusive) effect to facts established by final criminal judgments. Once a criminal conviction enters into legal force, the findings of the criminal court become binding upon civil courts, prosecutors, investigators, and other authorities without the need for additional evidentiary examination. In practice, these findings may subsequently be relied upon by courts, enforcement authorities, and other state institutions when ordering the confiscation or transfer of assets belonging to convicted individuals.

It should also be noted that the Russian media regularly reports allegations of corruption involving members of the judiciary. Corruption scandals involving members of parliament and the Federation Council likewise occur on a recurring basis. Although the Office of the Prosecutor General is one of the country's most influential institutions and serves as the principal authority responsible for combating corruption, Russian media outlets continue to report criminal cases involving prosecutors themselves.

7. Measures to Prevent the Misuse of Criminal Prosecution in Corporate Conflicts

1. Assign corporate disputes—including challenges to corporate resolutions, disputes concerning shareholders' interests, and claims for corporate damages—to the exclusive jurisdiction of the commercial (arbitrazh) courts.
2. Strengthen the institutional independence of the judiciary.
3. Improve the level of expertise of judges in courts of general jurisdiction in the fields of corporate and commercial law.
4. Introduce jury trials for selected economic offences, including abuse of authority, fraud, and related offences. (The Supreme Court of the Russian Federation proposed such a reform in 2020, but it has not been implemented.)
5. Promote greater consistency in judicial practice to prevent lower courts and law enforcement authorities from disregarding the interpretative guidance of the Plenum of the Supreme Court and the Constitutional Court, as well as from adopting arbitrary interpretations of the Criminal Code and the Criminal Procedure Code.
6. Strengthen the institutional independence of the prosecution service from investigative authorities.
7. Further develop mechanisms for reconciliation and settlement in criminal proceedings involving economic offences.